

PREDICTION AND VIDEO TRACKING OF DAMAGE ACCUMULATION IN HYBRID THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

Damage accumulation in a hybrid commingled fabric/GMT thermoplastic composite has been modelled with elastically damaging material models using FE analysis. The good accuracy of damage prediction has been confirmed by identifying with key events observed during video tracking and in the load-deflection data obtained during testing.

Keywords: thermoplastic composites, hybrid, damage, video, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composites (TPCs) are now being used widely in automotive applications. Semi-structural materials such as GMT and LFT, which can be moulded into relatively complex shapes, are now being complemented with more structural materials such as commingled fabric TPCs e.g. OCV Reinforcement's Twintex®, in hybrid material systems. The use of such hybrid composites does, however, present difficulties in design, specifically in the prediction of damage growth and failure. Greater understanding of the post-initial failure response of these materials is important for predicting their energy absorption. To address this issue, this paper reports on the development of finite element procedures, based on separate continuum damage models for each of the materials in the hybrid, to predict damage accumulation initially under quasi-static loading. The predictions are assessed for accuracy against load deflection data and video tracking of the damage events.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Materials and Manufacture

The material studied is a hybrid TPC sandwich structure as shown in Figure 1. This comprises structural skins of Twintex®, a 60 wt% E-glass/polypropylene, 2:2 balanced twill weave commingled fabric, supplied by OCV Reinforcements and a 40 wt% glass/polypropylene random GMT core, supplied by Quadrant Plastic Composites as GMT 40 PP. Following moulding to combine the materials, the nominal skin Twintex® thickness is 0.5 mm and GMT core thickness is 3.0 mm, giving a total hybrid nominal thickness of 4.0 mm.

Sandwich plaques were manufactured using a single stage compression moulding process following methods and processing conditions established by Wakeman [1]. The basic procedure involves preheating two square GMT blanks (191 mm x 191 mm) in an infra-red oven until they reach a temperature of 200°C as determined by an embedded thermocouple.. At this point the hot GMT blanks are stacked between two larger (210 mm x 210 mm) single plies of cold Twintex® and the whole stack is further heated until a temperature of 220°C is attained at the centre of the GMT. The material is then rapidly transferred to a circular tool in a press. Tool temperature is maintained at 80°C and 200 bar pressure is applied for 50 seconds. The GMT blank size has been chosen to ensure a nominal overall hybrid thickness of ~ 4 mm. Figure 1 shows the moulded plaque and a sectional view of the hybrid material.

Figure 1 Moulded hybrid material: (a) circular plaque; (b) cross-section

In addition to the moulding of the hybrid structure, monolithic GMT plaques are also moulded for comparison purposes. Six GMT blanks, 110 mm x 110 mm, are preheated to 220°C, transferred to the plaque tool, held at 50°C, and subjected to a pressure of 200 bar for 40 seconds. The results are a GMT plaque also of nominal thickness 4 mm. Manufacturing quality is assessed by determining void content in the specimens. Which are cut and polished following methods described in [2]. Optical images of the cross-sections analysed for void content using standard image thresholding techniques.

Specimens and Testing

Specimens, 80 mm long x 15 mm wide, are cut, using a band saw, from both the moulded hybrid and GMT plaques. For the hybrid specimens the fibre alignment is parallel and transverse to the main specimen axis. Specimens are tested in 3-point flexure to BS EN ISO 178:2003. Span is adjusted to ensure a span/depth ratio of 16:1 for all specimens.

Video Filming

During flexural testing, a JVC GR-DVL610 digital video camera with Tiffen 37 mm +2 lens is mounted on a tripod in front of the test machine and is used to capture localised

deformation and failure in the specimen in the vicinity of the central loading nose. Recording is synchronised with the test machine trace using audio signals from the machine. Video footage is output to a computer and snapshot images are obtained for specific features identified on the load-deflection curves.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Manufacturing Quality

Consolidation in both the moulded GMT and Hybrid plaques was found to be good with average void content levels of 1.19% (45 images) in GMT and 1.08% (60 images) in the Hybrid material.

Flexural Tests

Figures 2 (a) and 2(b) show the flexural test results (load-deflection) for the GMT and Hybrid material respectively. Results for 8 GMT specimens and 13 hybrid specimens are shown. For the hybrid specimens, two different sets are included. ‘+ face’ refers to a specimen tested with its upper face being the face contacting the mould surface. ‘- face’ refers to a specimen tested with its upper face being the face not contacting the mould. Because the ‘+ face’ contacting the mould cools faster, it is marginally thicker than the ‘- face’ which has time to consolidate more. However, the differences are small and have no systematic effect on the results. Table 1 summarises the key stiffness and strength data obtained from these graphs.

Table 1 Results of the Flexural Tests

Material	Flexural Modulus		Flexural Strength		Maximum Load	
	Mean (GPa)	Std. Dev. (GPa)	Mean (MPa)	Std. Dev. (MPa)	Mean (N)	Std. Dev. (N)
GMT	5.61	0.30 (5.3%)	148.7	7.1 (4.8%)	371.5	33.7 (9.1%)
HYBRID	8.58	0.20 (2.3%)	168.4	6.4 (3.8%)	482.3	20.5 (4.3%)

As expected, the hybrid material shows a significantly increased modulus and maximum load than the monolithic GMT. The increase is 53% in modulus and 30% in maximum load. The increase in flexural strength is not as pronounced, at 13% greater, due primarily to the limited compression strength of Twintex® giving failure on the upper loaded surface of the beam. More interesting are the comparative shapes of the load-deformation curves. GMT exhibits a sharper curve indicating more brittle failure beyond the peak load position at 6 to 8 mm deflection. The hybrid material, however, shows significant damage evolution beyond the initial failure peak with the curve flattening out before catastrophic failure takes place at 10 to 12 mm deflection. This gradual failure response for the hybrid would imply significantly greater energy absorption before failure which will be beneficial in impact/crash situations. The stochastic nature of the material is evidenced by significant variations in peak load and deflection at failure.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2 Flexural test results for (a) GMT and (b) Hybrid specimens

Video Tracking of Damage Accumulation

Figure 3 illustrates the results of the video tracking of the damage events taking place in the hybrid material during the 3-point flexure test, superimposed on the load deformation curve for the specimen. Snapshots of the video are taken at the times of several discernable events (8 in total) during loading and failure of the specimen. These events are:

Event 1: An audio cracking noise is heard on the video coinciding with a small load drop just beyond the linear elastic region of the load-deflection curve. There is no evidence of visual damage and it is likely to be a result of internal fibre breakage and/or resin cracking.

Event 2: Beyond event 1, audio cracking continues until further load drops are observed at event 2. This region is seen to coincide with a visible hump developing on the upper surface just to the left of the loading nose. This is clear evidence of fibre buckling under compression starting to take place.

Event 3: At this position on the load-deflection curve a larger load drop is observed which coincides on the video with more enhanced buckling in the position seen in event 2 and at a similar position to the right of the loading nose. Delamination between the Twintex® skin and the GMT core is also observable at these positions.

Event 4: The load drop observed at this event coincides with evidence of fibre breakage starting to occur on the bottom skin.

Event 5: The peak load which precedes major failure coincides on the video with significant fibre breakage in the bottom skin and complete cracking through its thickness.

Event 6: The end of event 5 indicated by load drop off to less than 50 % of its peak value and event 6 is coincident with complete failure of the bottom skin and some delamination between it and the core.

Event 7: Delamination between the bottom skin and core continues to develop and a crack is observed to grow upwards through the thickness of the GMT core.

Event 8: By this event the core crack has continued to grow deeply into the GMT core and a small residual load (~10% of the peak load) is supported almost solely by the buckled upper skin.

The video tracking has clearly shown the sequence of events of damage growth and failure in the hybrid structure and has related these events to specific observable load reductions on the load-deflection curve. In summary, the failure sequence initiates with upper skin compressive buckling and delamination from the core, followed by lower skin tensile fibre breakage and subsequent delamination from the core and, finally, core cracking growing upwards from the lower skin-core interface.

Figure 3 Failure sequence of hybrid material under 3-point flexure

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY

Figure 4 FEA model of hybrid material 3-point flexure test
(Twintex® skins – 1 layer; GMT core - 4 layers)

A 3D FEA model of the beam under 3-point flexure was built in ABAQUS/Standard implicit FEA package as shown in Figure 4. The aim of developing this model was to try to predict the localised damage mechanisms and their sequence described in the experimental section above.

The model comprises eight-noded 3D solid elements (C3D8I). A mesh sensitivity study showed that 10,000 elements for the full model (skins and core) resulted in acceptable stress conversion. The Twintex® skins comprise one layer of elements and the GMT core 4 layers of elements. A higher mesh density than this was chosen locally in the loading nose and support contact regions to ensure accuracy where the stress gradients are higher. Material models chosen were orthotropic for the Twintex® fabric skins and isotropic for the GMT core. Elastic and failure data for the two materials are given in the appendix.

A simplified failure and damage model was adopted for this initial study. The maximum normal stress initial failure criterion was used for both the Twintex® skins and GMT core. These criteria trigger an elastic damaging modulus degradation in a failing element by calling an appropriate user subroutine. If the failure is tensile, then the Young's modulus is reduced to 70% of its original value for GMT and 10% of its original value for Twintex®. If the failure is compressive, then the corresponding degradation values for compressive modulus are 25% of the original for GMT and again 10% for Twintex®. These values are chosen to best reflect the global reduction in load arising during the damaging region.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL RESULTS

Figure 5 Comparison of predicted and experimental load-deflection curves for the hybrid material under 3-point flexure

The FEA predicted load-deflection curve is compared with the experimental 3-point flexure test results in Figure 5. The predicted curve clearly shows the damage evolution with several load reductions following the elastic region. Peak load is also well predicted, bearing in mind the stochastic variability in the experimental curves. The load drop-offs can be identified with specific time increments during the analysis. Predicted damage progression in the material is shown in Figure 6, where damaged elements are highlighted in both the Twintex® skins and the GMT core. The damage events:

Time Increment 11: Initial failure occurs in the form of top skin compressive failure under the loading nose. Some damage in the adjacent GMT is also observed

Time Increment 17: A secondary region of top skin failure occurs a short distance from the loading nose damage, again also seen in the adjacent GMT. This corresponds to the experimentally observed localised top skin buckling and skin-core delamination

Time Increment 24: Bottom skin tensile failure damage is observed and spreads across the width of the skin. Increased compressive damage growth in top skin and GMT.

Time Increment 30: Secondary region and loading nose damage region link up in top skin and adjacent GMT resulting in major failure of top skin and skin-core delamination

Time Increment 50: Final failure of the model occurs in the form of complete failure of the top and bottom skins and extensive damage in the GMT. Excessive element distortion results in stopping of the analysis. On the predicted load-deflection curve (Figure 5), this increment corresponds to the major drop in load (~50%) observed in testing.

Figure 6 Damage progression in the hybrid material during 3-point flexure: (a) Twintex® skins; (b) GMT core

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The use of video in this study has enabled the evolution of damage events, during a flexural test, on a hybrid thermoplastic composite material structure, to be tracked and understood. Specific damage mechanisms, such as top skin compressive buckling, bottom skin tensile failure and core cracking have all been identified and their sequence of occurrence observed. The gradual nature of damage progression in these materials has been modelled by FEA using separate elastically damaging material models for the skin and core. The FEA model gives good predictions of the flexural load-deflection response of the material including the observable load drop-offs as damage mechanisms progress. Furthermore, the model allows damage to be tracked at an element level and the results, in terms of sequencing of damage progression, agree well with the experimental observations. At this stage, the damage models are relatively simple. Further work is underway to improve these models by using an interacting failure criteria for the Twintex® skins (e.g. Tsai-Wu) and developing a delamination model in order to predict delamination damage in the skin-core interface. However, notwithstanding these further developments, the methodology as it stands gives acceptable prediction of material response in the post initial failure region.

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APPENDIX

Table 2 Material property data used in the FE analyses

Material	Elastic Properties		Strength Properties	
GMT	E (GPa)	5.43	σ_T (MPa)	83.89
	ν	0.35	σ_C (MPa)	83.00
Twintex®	E_1 and E_2 (GPa)	13.38	σ_{11T} (MPa)	287.6
	E_3 (GPa)	2.94	σ_{11C} (MPa)	152.8
	ν_{12}	0.11	σ_{22T} (MPa)	287.6
	ν_{13} and ν_{32}	0.36	σ_{22C} (MPa)	152.8
	G_{12} (GPa)	1.66	σ_{33T} (MPa)	100
	G_{13} and G_{32} (GPa)	1.73	σ_{33C} (MPa)	100

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